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**THE CONCEPTUAL STRUCTURE OF THE SYSTEM OF SOCIAL
AND ECONOMIC SECURITY OF THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR:
PRINCIPLES, GUIDELINES, COMPOSITION**

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**КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОЕ СТРОЕНИЕ СИСТЕМЫ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНО-
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО СЕКТОРА:
ПРИНЦИПЫ, ОРИЕНТИРЫ, СОСТАВ**

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Abstract. Definition of socio-economic security of the industrial sector, presented by us, allowed us to qualify the outline and basis of the system structure (methodological, methodological, operational), the method of decomposition of the elemental composition. The goals of the system formation depend on the more significant and large-scale tasks of the social and economic security of the industrial sector, which determines the purpose of the system. At the same time, the difficulties of socio-economic security are formulated from 2 positions. To begin with, from the point of view of the defense of state socio-economic interests and the industrial sector as a carrier of these interests. In-2, based on the need to maintain the performance of the industrial sector at a non-hazardous level. In coordination with the acquired results, we developed the structural and logical scheme of forming of the system of ensuring the social and economic safety of industrial sector.

Аннотация. Дефиниция социально-экономической безопасности промышленного сектора, представленная нами, разрешила квалифицировать очертание и основы системного строения (методологических, методических, операционных), метод декомпозиции элементного состава. Цели формирования системы находятся в зависимости от более весомых и масштабных задач социально-экономической безопасности промышленного сектора, что и определяет назначение системы. При этом трудности социально-экономической безопасности формулируются с двух позиций. Для начала, с точки зрения обороны государственных социально-экономических интересов и промышленного сектора как носителя данных интересов. Во-вторых, исходя из надобности поддержания характеристик функционирования промышленного сектора на неопасном уровне. В согласовании с приобретенными итогами, нами разработана структурно-логическая схема формирования системы обеспечения социально-экономической безопасности промышленного сектора.

Keywords: socio-economic security, government, society, enterprise, employee, threat, security, interests, economics, analysis, system.

Ключевые слова: социально-экономическая защищенность, государство, общество, предприятие, работник, угроза, защищенность, интересы, экономика, анализ, система.

The functioning of the industrial sector is related to processes that are ready to generate all sorts of dangers. Their features determine the range of tactical and strategic objectives of ensuring the socio-economic security of the industrial sector. So, for example, dangers that are implemented in the structure and internal environment of the industrial sector, identify tactical objectives that are focused on the destruction in the short term manifested adverse trends [1, p. 245; 2; 3, p. 70].

Specificity of these tasks lies in the fact that their resolution is matched with absolute information help — the danger has manifested, its origin and background are clear, the results can be evaluated with a sufficient degree of probability. As a result, the decision is guaranteed by the implementation in the short term of appropriate targeted measures of financial, economic, managerial and political nature, the adoption of which is based on a relatively reliable array of information. The risks are likely to urge longer time frames to identify, describe and assess the extent of adverse capacity. Individual scientists set the stage for an impartial assessment of risks of socio-economic nature up to 20 years [4, p. 16]. Accordingly, the tasks of preventing them are strategic. This is explained by the fact that the information used for the study of probable dangers is incomplete and its reliability is usually not easy to determine. At the same time, the implementation of the probable dangers is justified by the abundance of obvious and implicit moments, the composition of which is formed by accident. Due to the fact that the sources of danger have a chance to purchase both a subjective and an objective character, the determinations lie in the plane of the strategic objectives provide socio-economic security [5, p. 4]. The essence of relations between the country and economic entities in the production sphere largely depends on their results. Based on the formulated criteria for the implementation of the property of the security of the system, the provisions of the approach of functionality in terms of the guidelines of social formation and the results of ensuring socio-economic security, the following redistribution of tasks to ensure socio-economic security of the industrial sector is proposed (Figure 1.). The solution of tactical and strategic tasks of ensuring socio-economic security is associated with the need to develop an appropriate methodological framework.

Formed methodological approaches contain provisions that logically apply to the formation of the system.

However, none of them is considered to be integrating in a similar construction. As a result, the author suggests the alignment, which determines the natural basis of the structure of ensuring socio-economic security of the industrial sector. The essence of the alignment is that the division between the subject and object areas of socio-economic security is made and the condition of the effectiveness of the mechanism of ensuring socio-economic security is put forward. To do this, fundamentally clarify the concept of socio-economic security in relation to the specificity of the industrial sector. Taking into account the results of the object identification, the socio-economic security of the industrial sector is considered by us as conditioned by the fundamental changes in the internal and external environment of its production, credit, financial and innovative potential, allowing the structure as a whole to preserve the dynamic socio-economic stability, and, in addition, the quality of adaptability and self-reproduction [6].

Figure 1. Basic tasks of ensuring social and economic security of the industrial sector.

Source: author's development.

Definition of socio-economic security of the industrial sector, presented by us, allowed us to qualify the outline and basis of the system structure (methodological, methodological, operational), the method of decomposition of the elemental composition. The goals of the system formation depend on the more significant and large-scale tasks of the social and economic security of the industrial sector, which determines the purpose of the system. At the same time, the difficulties of socio-economic security are formulated from 2 positions. To begin with, from the point of view of the defense of state socio-economic interests and the industrial sector as a carrier of these interests. In-2, based on the need to maintain the performance of the industrial sector at a non-hazardous level. In coordination with the acquired results, we developed the structural and logical scheme of forming of system of ensuring social and economic safety of the industrial sector (Figure 2.). Guidelines for structuring the element base of ensuring social and economic security are guided by the focus of priority financial and economic interests, because they mediate the logic of interelement interaction in the financial and economic system of the society. In other words, these interests lie in the basis of the social choice of methods of ensuring state security and its various varieties. Our analysis of the provisions of the political documents of a number of States that determine the basis of their socio-economic security, illustrated that they are aimed at an array of priority financial and economic interests (1-5), [7-8].

Figure 2. Structurally-logic scheme of formation of the system of ensuring socio-economic security of the industrial sector

Source: author's development

Classification of these interests and testing of correlation with the objects of defense demonstrates that, subject to coordination with the goals of social formation, they have every chance to be used as strategic and tactical guidelines for ensuring socio-economic security. This choice is confirmed by the fact that in the program documents of social and economic formation of the Republic of Belarus strategic guidelines are formulated according to the idea of defense of state interests accepted by society [8]. Tactical guidelines lie in the plane of one of the elements of state interests — the financial and economic interests of the industrial sector. When they are specified, the object of financial and economic interests is formed, the choice of which is obliged to meet the claims of strategic guidelines. Hence, the goals of social formation are also determined and tactical guidelines, the composition of which is justified by the current interests of the industrial sector of the country.

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